

Library Movement in Bangladesh: The Development Thought of Bangabandhu

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Abstract:

The contribution of books and libraries in our lives is immense. Through books and libraries, we establish our past and history and create hints about future possibilities. An author of a book explains his experience in the book. In the book we share the experiences of the knowledgeable and benefit from the way we live. A library is with a collection of diverse books, a summary of all the experiences, knowledge and discovery of the world. The vast ocean of a library is flooded with all the tools of the various branches of national life. The identity of man is not only about his present moment, but also his past, present and future. Knowing the past, we must find a close connection with the great current that flows from the beginning of the human creation to the present and we will be able to discover ourselves in the true context. We can awaken our world as a connected human being. The past of human civilization can be enlightened through books and libraries. In the present moment, as the future of some of the past's thoughts, at some point in the future, the present thinking will be the subject of the past. This article is an effort to make this effort a wake-up call to the future by determining the line of library development in Bangladesh. The efforts of those who have been constantly touched by the development of the drawn line were from the distant past to the present day, our nation's father, The Great Sheikh Mujibur Rahman. The book was an essential tool in his political and family life. The family library at Dhanmondi 32 is a unique resource of life of the family. His 1313-day relentless efforts are described in the sharp-moving article.

Keywords: Public Library, Library Science, Education System, Library Movement, Library Development.

Introduction

According to scientists, the current evolution of mankind is about 10,000 years old. But in the world of the library, the first library was created in the Sumeri region of Egypt and in the Asia Miner. The first institutional library was established in the World by Emperor Assurbonipal in 625 BC in Nineveh, Egypt. A national library was established in China in the 1st century B.C. The library was built in the world at the age of 25,000. The library is associated with the deep and inherent the development of the ancient civilization of mankind. Civilization would not have been developed unless the middle library of the generation from generation to generation was a bridge. The library has developed the development of civilization in a rapid and age-old way. Needless to say, it is essential to discuss the history, heritage, literature and culture of the subcontinent in order to illustrate the development of the library of Bangladesh. The development of libraries described in the history of the ancient stochastic of about 4000 to 5000 years is not very insignificant. The history of the library of India is very ancient. From the beginning, there were attempted to preserve various types of 'Puthi' (manuscripts) and books in the temples, monasteries, mosques, churches and other religious temples and collection of educated scholars.¹ Library development started in Bangladesh about 2000 years ago. In the 3rd century BC, the library was found in different Buddhist Behar (monasteries) including the Region of Mainamati and Mahasthangarh. Especially in the Buddhist-Behar libraries, there is evidence of the coming of people who are in the ranks of knowledge-oriented people from different countries to collect knowledge from the materials stored in the libraries. The story of the famous Chinese explorer Fa-Hyen in 399 B.C. is a way to know the existence of the library in Bangladesh.² Also, Hyun Sang came in the 7th century to use the Buddhist Behar library in the region for greater experience and knowledge of Buddhism. From the description, the library of the Subcontinent of India and Bangladesh can be seen as the development.

At this stage, the library development phase in Bangladesh is divided into five categories and the search process is described:

1. Prehistoric Period
2. British Colonial Period

3. Pre-Independence (1947-1971)
4. Post Independence up to '75 (1313 Days) and
5. Period from '75 to present time.

1. Prehistoric Period

The awakening of this subcontinent on the highway of world civilization is one of the most spectacular wonders of the renaissances and history of human life style and civilization. After the death of human being, 'psychological memory is the same with the human body. So the memory of the human of the age-changing period of civilization, the experiences, the thought, the consciousness, the inspiration and the feeling, the creative follow-up, the realization of the future for the successors, the future generations and the human society, were created by establishing the library. In the dark, they are used in the way of preserving the overall development of human consciousness and intelligence for the successors. Clay Tablets of Middle Asia, or the papyrus of Egypt, is the best example of earliest civilization of human beings. There were a process of collection of materials and still collected, the subject based arrangement and layout of the system can be seen to ensure proper use.

Library management was one of the earliest sciences of the early metaphysical sciences that helpful to creation and flourishing of civilization. The library does not have an alternative to the right direction of implementation of human philosophy. It is undeniable to say that they are organized from the time when people's thoughts and consciousness are blown. The progress of the library in the process of knowledge practice, exercise and conservation of knowledge in the course of history has accelerated the evolution of civilization.

So there comes a time when requirements arose to library organization become immense necessary. Hence, the practice of library organization strategy is one of the most important trends in the evolving stream of human civilization, besides the vast gain of knowledge from ancient times. In this sequence a library has been able to grow beautifully; otherwise, civilization would have been abandoned as a waste. When a library is organized, it has a collection of less, limited demand, less work space. Day by day, the need increases and the work are increased. The need for that provision and the demand for services have been increased in a multiplicity, as well as the collection of a library. According to the fifth principle of Ranganathan, the collection became a 'mahiruh'. So the library organization's requirements are well and well-regulated in order to provide the readers with the information they need at the right time.

The expansion of Buddhist Bihars in the Indian subcontinent and various regions of Bangladesh has been mainly the basis of knowledge practice in this country and have preserved the essence of development of ancient civilizations going on. It is claimed that the library was started in Bangladesh about to 2,000 years ago. But for whatever reason, the growth trend has not been able to spread.

2. British Colonial Period

The world and civilization have evolved; Human civilization has been damaged by various visible-invisible disasters, including war, natural disasters. Civilization has been destroyed many times. Again, the new awakening has led to a great explosion of civilization, as the invasion of imperialism has disrupted the education, culture, and customs of the country as well of the nation. The colonial rule, aggression, and the forced strategy have degraded the elements of development. During the rule of the British imperialists for almost two hundred years, exploitation has been more than the physical progress of the subcontinent and the present Bangladesh. It is worth mentioning that the British were too afraid of being disobedient to the development. Especially not found much interest in building educational institutions, including the establishment of libraries. The development that can be seen is only in the effort to keep the British regime alive.

The library movement in Bangladesh started a little in the early nineteenth century. During this time, there are many places where different libraries are established. At that time, some libraries were established with direct or indirect financial assistance from the British. During the first decade of the Nineteenth, the public library was established in three major cities Kolkata, Bombay and Madras of India. The library movement expanded in the thirties. During this period, between Lord William Bentinck's departure from India and Lord Auckland's arrival in India (March 1835-February 1836), Sir Charles Theophilus Metcalfe was appointed as the chief of staff for a year. This is the time when a great event is organized; In 1823, Bombay and in 1827 the freedom of printing was repealed and the printing press was given full freedom to the printer throughout India.³ On 3 August 1835, the act became a statutory act that implemented on 15 September. The native and foreign people organized many meetings as a sign of joy and gratitude in Kolkata, the capital of India. For this purpose, the general meeting held at Calcutta Town Hall on 20 August 1835 decided that a building called the Metcalfe Library Building would be built in the heart of Calcutta to mark the gratitude of Metcalfe and the library would be established for the general public.⁴ Later it was originally converted to Calcutta Public Library. The library was opened on 8 March 1836. This was the first truly established public library in undivided Bengal.⁵

In Britain, the Perth Public Library Act was approved by Parliament in 1850. A year later, in 1851, a public library was established in Jessore for the first time. The introduction of this law has led to a wide spread in the public education

system. In that case, the movement to establish libraries was also started in India, of the then zamindar, umedar, social worker, government officials and public figures initiated to establish libraries. In 1854, the public library was established at three other district headquarters. They were woodburnpublic library, which had 25,000 books, Rangpur Public Library and Barisal Public Library and two libraries with collections of 19,800 and 17,200 books respectively. 1854 was considered as a milestone in the history of library development of Bangladesh. In the district, mahkuma (subdivision) and some police stations, libraries are seen to be established. The Library movement was rapidly flourished in 1884 and 1885, by the establishment of Rajshahi and Comilla Public Library respectively. In 1897, the Public Library of Sylhet and the Noakhali Public Library were established.⁶

Besides the establishment of the Public Library, several colleges and related libraries were established before the establishment of Dhaka University in East Bengal. That's already passed the century of tradition. Among them is Dhaka College (1841), Jagannath College (1844), Rajshahi College (1873), Barisal Brajomohan College (1889), M.C. College (1892) in Sylhet, Pabna Award College (1889), Comilla Victoria College (1899).

Meanwhile, when the Press and Registration Book Act were passed in 1867, a strong move was initiated to speed up the library movement. Later, in 1872-76, the Governor of India Northbark Hall Loibri was established in the Bangla bazaar of Dhaka, on the banks of Buriganga. The library was then the centre of cultural practice of the residents of Dhaka. In 1882, the Banari Para Public Library of Barisal, Anand Agovind Public Library in Pabna, and The Umesh Chandra Public Library in Khulna were established in 1897. Between 1884 and 1915, several more libraries were established in different parts of the region. Among them, the Natore Victoria Public Library (1887), the Nilfamari Public Library (1891), and the Western Diamond Jubilee Library and Club (1898) was established in Bhola.

The trend of library movements in Bangladesh in particular was seen to be moving a little bit in the early 20th century. Among them, the Victoria Memorial Public Library in Korigram (1901), the Buckland Public Library (1904) in the Port City Chittagong, after a long time Chitagong Public Library was established in 1963. The Cox Bazar Public Library was established in 1906. The Ram Mohan Public Library by the Brahmo Society at Patuatuli in Dhaka in 1905, the Gaybanda Public Library (1907), the Harendralal Public Library established by the author of Dhaka District Gazette and the then District Magistrate B.C. Allen of Munshiganj in 1908, the Parymohan Samobay Public Library (1910) in Nogaon, Lalmonirhat Public Library (1911), The Barendra Museum Research Library (1910) in the area of Rajshahi, Raninagarpur and Gurudaspur Public Library (1915) were established. In 1912, Shri Mahesh Chandra Bhattacharya, then social Philanthropist of Comilla, established the 'Ram Mala Library' in the name of his mother. The Dhaka Museum Library was established in 1913.

From 1906 to 1911, the Maharaja of Boroda took specific action to promote and establish the library movement. Sir III Siyajirao also took the first major step in the introduction of the library system in 1910. In 1911, the first library science education was taken up under the supervision of W.C. Borden. Then the library science education system was started in Punjab and Madras respectively in 1915 and 1929, and training was started in Lahore under the supervision of American Librarian Asa Don Dickinson. Khan Bahadur Asadullah Khan, the founder of the Kolkata Imperial Library, also famous for his work as the founder of the Indian Library movement, including many famous librarians in Bangladesh received training on Library Science from there.

Due to the influence of the library movement, the then Indian government organized the Nikhil Bharat Library Conference in 1918. It was held in Lahore from January 4-8. The conference was attended by representatives of central and local governments, universities and leading public libraries. The conference adopted a proposal to introduce a service based on cooperation between the small libraries by introducing the regional library system through a central library.⁷ It was a constitutional act. After that, the Autonomy Act 1885 was amended in 1919 and the responsibility of the libraries were imposed on the district board and the municipality.⁸

In 1921, the non-cooperation movement launched by Mahatma Gandhi was effectively encouraged to create the library movement in Bangladesh. The effort stake in the library creation in Bangladesh was not a small one in the decade ago. But then the library movement was not concentrated in Bangladesh. The movement was divided and scattered. All Bengal Library Association was established in 1925 to promote the organized library movement in Bangladesh.⁹

The library was expanded in Bangladesh due to the influence of the movement. In this decade, the British government has issued an ordinance to establish Dhaka University. Dhaka University was started in 1921 and library service was also introduced. Dhaka University Library is the prime recognition of the library movement of Bangladesh. In the middle of this decade in 1924, with the help of several patriotic workers with enthusiasm, the library service of free money was launched in some places with branches for the public in Madaripur district of Faridpur District. It is reported that there were attempts to establish such libraries in some other districts at that time.¹¹ The Rajbari Mahakuma Library Conference was held in Baliakandi village in Faridpur district in June 1925. The proposal to form a Mahakuma Library Council was accepted at this conference. . . . Some of the organized library movements were started in Bangladesh before the first Bengali Library Conference (in December 1925) was held to promote library movement across the country.¹²

Before the partition of India, there was one pablic library in almost all district headquarters in present Bangladesh. They are still running as public or private libraries.

The movement of the library was in progress until 1942. But during World War-II, some of the relaxation in the movement came down. On the other hand, the Hindu-Muslim conflict arose a few days after the end of war. This also fails to keep pace with the movement and leads to a rise in the number of people living in the area. The movement is very much lag behind.¹³ The government created the Primary Education Act in 1930, which opened the opportunity for the expansion of public education. This led to a wide spread of education, literature and culture in East Bengal. One statistic shows that in 1941, 61 libraries were found in Barisal and Potuyakhali areas, 32 in Bogra, 25 in Dhaka district, 39 in Mymensingh district, 23 in Faridpur, 48 in Rajshahi, 26 in Rangpur, 51 in Kushtia and Dinajpur, then 15 and 21 libraries established in Sylhet and Noakhali respectively. In addition, 121 public and private libraries are also scatteredly found in existence from different sources. Many of them are now extinct. But until 1947, more than 335 private public libraries were found in India. Local influential zamindars, umedar, social philanthropists and educated individuals or families have been supporting these libraries for a long time. As of today, there are more than 5000 Government public libraries in India and 2480 Government and aided public libraries in West Bengal under National Mission on Libraries (NML).

3. Pre-Independence (1947-1971)

In 1947, India was divided on 14th August. Library development has not yet been activated in then East Pakistan. In effect, the libraries of Punjab, Lahore and Dhaka University were very lively. But the first ten years of the struggle for the survival of Pakistan were almost over.¹⁴ Pakistan has not given much attention to the development and establishment of the library at this time. In fact, like other wealth and property sharing, the loss of the share of the Indian libraries of the British era is very much lost. Pakistan has not received any part of the Imperial Library in Kolkata (now Indian National Library), Indian Museum and Central Government Library located in Delhi and other cities.¹⁵ But on the other hand, India has received a fair share of the burden of the government museums and libraries in Lahore.¹⁶ The present Bangladesh's long-term development of the library has been in the making miserable state since then. Besides, Pakistan was seen to be troubled in the country due to internal political unrest. In particular, the political activity of the then East Pakistan has so much to do with the Pakistani ruling group that it was not enough to focus on the development of the library and the establishment of new libraries. It is also noted that the library has not been provided with proper time, labour and sufficient funds for the development. East Pakistan was also a victim of deliberate negligence and discrimination of Central Government of Pakistan.

It is worth mentioning that in 1949, the Government of Pakistan established the Directorate of Archives and Libraries under the Ministry of Education. At the same time, the National Library of Pakistan was established in Karachi. Though the present Central Public Library was established in 1953, but except this, there was no significant plan for the development of the overall library sector. In fact, the Pakistani regime has not shown much interest in creating a fair political environment for planning. During this time, the birth of the Awami Muslim League was a new dimension in the politics of the Muslim League. On 23 February 1948, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman immediately protested when Prime Minister Khaja Nazimuddin declared at the Legislative Council that "people of East Pakistan will accept Urdu as a national language". Protests erupted across the country. On 2 March, in order to further organize the movement against the Muslim League, the Muslim group of activists met at the Fazlul Haq Muslim Hall. At that meeting, the 'All Party National Language Action Council' was formed on the proposal of Sheikh Mujibur Rahman. The country was divided on the question of the language of the country. The whole country was then excited about the demand for the state language Bengali. During the mass strike on 11 March, the unquestionable leader of Bengal, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, along with some other fellow soldiers, was detained in Dhaka central prison; It lasts for a long time (about two years and five months). On 26 January 1952, in protest against the declaration of 'The state language of Pakistan will be Urdu', Sheikh Mujib called on the State Language Action Council to celebrate the release of the king on 21 February and the demand for the state language of Bangla. On 14 February, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman went on hunger strike in prison for 13 days. He was transferred to the Faridpur jail for the reason of contacting the protesters. Students' Association brought out a procession to make Bengali language a state language on 21 February. Police shot at the march after breaking Section 144. On this day Salam, Jabbar, Barkat, Rafiq, Shafiur and many others were achieved status of the state language of Bangla in East Bengal after given a huge bloodshed. The reference to Bengali lifestyle, literature and culture is the same, and the need for free thought and expression of consciousness is essential. The sacrifice of Sheikh Mujib in establishing this language is unforgettable. The Bengali stoicism was established because of the fact that the Bengali language was able to keep the demand intact. In Bangladesh, the field of literature and culture was expanded. Bengalis were able to keep their own self-interest in the Bengali literature and culture in their own language.

Pakistanis did not stop harassing Sheikh Mujib even after he was released on the demand and pressure of movement on 26 February. The status of Bengali language is kept unspoiled in exchange for many bloods. But due to political unrest, there may not be any plans to develop the library. The article notes that the literature and publishing industry is not only involved in language but also complements each other. And the library development is also related to publishing. This is why Sheikh Mujibur Rahman is seen to be more vocal. He understood that the nation's culture and history, literature was created based on language. The autonomy of the country and nation is meaningless without freedom of language.

Sheikh Mujibur Rahman thought that the library was the repository and carrier of the creation of literature, culture and history of the nation. Even though this realization did not make anyone else look like a man, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman realized what a library holds in the prison. We saw what forms of books and libraries had linked in his life.

With continued struggle and effort, the then East Pakistan (currently Bangladesh) plan to set up a public library at four divisional headquarters was conceived in 1953 by the Director of Education in Pakistan. Later in the year 1958 and 1962-63, postgraduate diploma and masters degree courses were started in the library science under Dhaka University. In 1953, the process of setting up the first Central Public Library in Dhaka began. On 5 February 1954, as minister of the United Front, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman laid the foundation stone of the public library and unveiled a mile plaque in the history library movement. In 1854, after a hundred years, the undisputed leader of this country officially established the government library in East Bengal and created a glorious example. The library was established at a cost of Rs 13 lakh. But the door of the library's reader service was opened in 1958 and Mr. Ahmad Hussain joined as the first librarian. He earned an M.S degree from Columbia University in the United States in 1955 before becoming a librarian. In 1962 the library building was transferred to Dhaka University. Under the five-year plan of 1955-59, the public space of the library was now set up in Shahbag. Finally, in January 1978, Public library was shifted to the existing building in Shahbag after leaving the building.¹⁸ The education adviser of the President, Syed Ali Ahsan, formally inaugurated the present Central Public Library in Shahbag on 6 January 1978 for public use. On 30 June 1954, Mr. Muhammad Siddique Khan (MS Khan) went to the United Kingdom to earn a higher degree and returned on 30 June 1954 and took over as a librarian of Dhaka University.

In 1955, the Government of Pakistan was appointed LC Key, an Assistant Librarian of the National Library of Australia, to survey the country's library service. The survey was completed in 1956 but the recommendations of the report were not published at the time. The first 3 month certificate course was introduced in 1952 by the Late Mr. Fazle Elahi, the then- renowned Senior Librarian of Dhaka University, for the study of library science. Later in the 1955-56 academic years, Miss Millered L. Methvan taught the certificate course as a teacher at the Fulbright Scholarship Program. In 1958, the full curriculum was started through the Department of Library Science at Dhaka University. This was a six-month certificate course.¹⁹

In the early 20th century, some library was established in the district and the Mahakuma level. Some of these are marked as the municipal library; Includes Habigonj Public Library in Sylhet, Sylhet Municipal Library, Chandpur Municipal Public Library of then Comilla District, Narayangonj Municipal Library, Rangpur Municipal Library. These libraries were mainly used to bear the burden of public donations and unregulated government grants. It has been mentioned earlier that the plan to set up a government library was taken up at four divisional headquarters by the order of the Director of Education in Pakistan. As a result, the process of setting up the Central Public Library in Dhaka was first started in 1953. It is worth mentioning that in 1954, many others including Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, led by the leader of the United Front, Sher-e-Bangla Abul Kasemul Haque, won the election. Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was also a member of the United Front Cabinet. It is a reminder that in 1854, just 100 years after the three mass libraries at the district level, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman laid the foundation stone of the Central Public Library on 5th February 1954. Though its reader service was opened in 1958. The Chittagong Divisional Public Library was established in 1963 and the Khulna Divisional Public Library was established in 1965. The library service has not improved much except the steps taken in the meantime.²⁰

Highlights the development of the college library and the higher education and training of the staff in the First Five Year Plan of the then Pakistan Government. The same arrangement was put in place in the second five year plan of 1960-65. In June 1968, Professional and medium level library officers and staff were evaluated and considered as Teaching Staff category. And the pay structure was also changed and fitted in.²¹ But after the establishment of the Central Public Library, there was no improvement in library development and movement. In that case, the central government's inaction was evident. After 1965, there was a slight change in the attitude of the government. The library service is considered as a part of education in the third five year plan. With this, the main plan for setting up and developing libraries at various levels was adopted in the appropriate manner. At that time, a plan was also adopted in the provincial capital Dhaka to establish the National Library and to develop and reform 36 colleges. But nothing of that proposed plan was implemented. Besides, under the fourth five year plan of 1970-1975, the proposal was adopted to develop libraries in Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna and Rajshahi and to form separate departments. But that plan has not been implemented.

In undivided India, some special libraries were established. Under the supervision of the then Deputy Commissioner, a large library was built in the Commissioner's office in Dhaka in 1857 and at the Collectorate of Rajshahi in 1865. Dhaka Bar Library was established in 1900. Besides, another special library was found, the library of the Rajshahi Commissioner's Office was established in 1947 and at the same time the library of the Bangladesh High Court Bar Association was established. Except these, there no other library has been established but they do not exist anywhere in East Bengal. But after 1947, 18 institutions were found to have established the Connected Library. Among them, The Secretariat, Bangladesh Assembly House, Land Records and Survey Library are notable. Apart from this, the Jute Research Institute and the Asiatic Society Library were established in 1957. The University of Dhaka's I.B.A. library

was established in 1966 and the BIDS received donations given by Ford Foundation in 1972-73 and 73-74. . . . As of 1970, 121 special libraries were found available.²²

Earlier, in July 1954, some professionals sit together in a meeting at the Palasi Barracks in Dhaka and had planned to establish a library association. Among members are Abdur Rahman Merdha, A.M. Shamsul Haque, Rakib Hussain, Siddique Ahmed Chowdhury, Jamil Khan, Abdur Rab and Tofazl Hossain. The following year an adhoc committee was formed under the leadership of Dr. Nafis Ahmed, head of Geography Department at Dhaka University and part-time Librarian. Other members of the committee were Ahmed Hussain, Abdur Rahman Merdha, Rakib Hussain, A.M. Motahar Ali Khan and Nargis Zafar. At this time, the Regional Library Association was proposed to the East Pakistan Library Association. In January 1956 a three-member sub-committee was formed to draft the proposed East Pakistan Library Association. The committee consisted of Ahmed Hussain, Abdur Rahman Merdha and Rakib Hussain was supported by Shamszam Ansari, Reader of the Law Department of Dhaka University. The East Pakistan Library Association was formed on the basis of their recommendations. The draft constitution of the Society was approved at the first annual general meeting held at the USIS Headquarters in Dhaka on 30th June 1956.

The first working council of the East Pakistan Library Association (Bangladesh Library Association (LAB) formed at the annual general meeting held on July 1956 and the then Librarian Md. Siddique Khan of Dhaka University, the Chief Librarian of the USIS, Rakib Hussain and the Assistant Librarian of Dhaka University Library, Abdur Rahman Merdha were selected as President, the Secretary and Treasurer respectively in the committee. The committee was 15 members. The first conference was held in Dhaka on 24-28 December 1960 in collaboration with the Pakistan Library Association, in collaboration with the East Pakistan Library Association. The main guest at the event was then the Governor of Pakistan, Lt. Gen. Md Azam Khan. In 1963, the East Pakistan Library Association organized the second conference in Dhaka.

The far-reaching attitude of the Pakistani ruling group to behave and degrade was not realized by library professionals at that time. All the discrimination between the country's conscious people and politicians became clear. At this time Sheikh Mujibur Rahman declared his historic 6th points of the nation in 1966 to help Pakistanis to avoid discriminations. This is treated as the certificate of release of the Bengali (Muktir Sanad) from the oppression of Pakistan. In six points, focuses the literature of the Bengalis, the history-culture, the political and socio-economic development of the country. The most profound theory is the dream of Bangla and Bengali and awakens to achieve independency. The political situation in the country is further complicated by the fact that it is in a state of flux; Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was arrested on a number of occasions for various reasons and conspiracy. The middle of repression of the people of East Bengal has increased the level of oppression. The political agenda still hasn't stopped. But Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was arrested on a number one charge in the Agarhtala conspiracy case on 3 January 1968. On January 17, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was released and then arrested again from the jail gate and detained in an unknown location inside the Dhaka Cantonment. The trial began on June 19 in a fierce run-off.

On 5th January 1969, the All Party Student Action Council of Dhaka University united and strengthened the 11points movement alongwith 6 points of Sheikh Mujib. The All Party Student Action Council continued to carry out the slogan 'Break the lock of the jail, bring Sheikh Mujib'. This movement took place in the mass uprising of '69. On February 22, the Pakistani Government withdrew the Agartala conspiracy case and released all the accused, including Sheikh Mujib, in the face of the continued public outing. On February 23, the Central Student Action Council arranged to give a worm reception to Sheikh Mujibur Rahman at the Racecourse Ground. In the presence of 1 million students and people at the reception, leader of the All-Party Student Action Council, Mr. Tofael Ahmed was awarded Sheikh Mujib the honor "Banglabandhu". Thus the perception of Pakistan's division became more clear.

After the 1970 elections, the issue of division continued to move towards the end. Despite the large number of people in the assembly elections, the people of the country and the country united in their call for full independence from the demand for independence with six points due to the Pakistanis' unilateral attitude towards the power. After nine months of struggle, the free Bangladesh of the red sun-lit flag was achieved on 16 December 1971 in exchange for the sacrifice of 3 million people and the humiliation of more than two lakh mothers and sisters. "The reference to note is that Bangladesh has not yet received any share of the resources and property for library service from Pakistan since its inception."²³

In 1971, soon after Bangladesh gained independence, the East Pakistan Library Association was renamed and the Bangladesh Library Association (LAB) was established. After that, the Bangladesh Library Association received the recognition of the International Library Association (IFLA) and the Commonwealth Library Association (COMLA) in 1976.

In 2004 the constitution of the society was changed; one of the main issues of change was the direct voting rights instead of postal ballot. The second amendment is to replace the 15 member executive council with a 16 member executive council. Elections are held according to the amended constitution. The 16 member executive council was elected by direct vote of the members. The two are the ones who The 10th General Assembly held on February 5, 2011, was approved by 21 members of the Central Functional Council of the organization. Besides the President, The Secretary General and the Treasurer, the committee will include three vice presidents, one joint secretary general, one organizing

secretary, one women affairs secretary, and a total of four secretaries and 11 councilors. Of these, 5 central councilors and six posts are reserved for six departments of the country. Another councilor's position was increased due to the increase in administrative division. The 22 member executive council was formed during the 2012-2014 elections. Again, the 2014-2017 Executive Council was re-appointed as a divisional councilor. The 23 member working council was reformed by increasing the number of members of the Council. The Executive Council is elected for three years at the annual general meeting of the Association.

The executive committee of the Association consists of 21 members. Along with President, General Secretary and Treasurer, there are three Vice-Presidents, one Assistant General Secretary, one Organizing Secretary including four Secretaries and ten other councilors. Six posts of councilors are distributed among six divisions of Bangladesh. The committee is elected for a three-year term.

3. Post Independence-until 15 August '75 (1313 days)

The conspiracy against language, the 11 points of the All Party Student Action Council with 6 points of the freedom certificate of the Bangabandhu created an agitation, the victory of the 70s and the mandate of government formation, the war of independence in the hope of freedom from the long-term oppression of the People; Bangladesh gained independence in exchange for blood of a sea of 3 million martyrs. The country was liberated from the long-term slavery trap. Bangladesh today stands on the world map after a nine month struggle. But in the newly independent Bangladesh, the body of the broken-down is destroyed. The Pakistani Hyena troop has left the country in a state of shock. Wherever you look, you see the burning debris, the smell of rotting bodies and the burning of the burnt soil. The day the 'Bangabandhu returned to the country' (on 10 January 1972) still smelled of the rotten and decaying bodies and gun powder in the sky and air. The sad earth's goblets are a testimony to the terrible times of weeping and the sedition of the ruins. The day he cried, "what do I see in this?" For more than half of his life, he has spent more than half his life living within four walls jail, so that the beloved people of the country can live happily, prosperous and better lives, smile, play in the open air, and eat meal at least twice in a day. The Bangabandhu dreamed of these people. And he thought when he could make people of country human beings. But what is he seeing with his feet on the ground? He cried in the manner of a stretch and he made his mind up on what he shall have to do the next day. He thought himself how to build the nation. And he didn't have to look back. On 12 January 1972, the Prime Minister of Bangladesh took over. The country is in the grip of a rebuilding of its allies. On 14th December, the first constitution of Bangladesh was signed by Bangabandhu. The constitution came into effect on 16th December. He ordered the creation of a short and long-term first five year plan for the development of the economic infrastructure. It is worth noting that during the nine month war, the country's socio-economic infrastructure was destroyed, including numerous libraries connected to schools, colleges, universities. In these considerations, the plan was adopted on the orders of the Prime Minister to rebuild the country. In light of the five-year plan, the government of the state of Bangladesh formed an Education Commission led by Dr. Kudrat-e-Khuda with a far-sighted and far-reaching approach, especially in the light of the five-year plan. The Commission submitted the report on 24 September 1972.

The Commission's report reflects the growing concern of the Bangladesh Library Development. The Bangabandhu believed in the idea that the library system of the destroyed country could be changed in the absence of a war that was in vain. So, considering that the Commission is doing the right thing, the reality is still unacceptable.

It provides that the library of any research and administrative institution, including educational institutions, is recognized as the 'heart of the concerned institution'. Most of our education and institutions are heart-rending. Especially to make the education system more practical and self-serving, we need to be re-arranged. In this belief, the self-styled and confident Bangabandhu welcomed the Education Commission.

The report also specifies the scope or standard of library development so that all the development staff and administration authorities concerned can come up with a clear idea of development and provide some equality between the libraries of educational institutions. The standard indicated requires a review every five years; this is the idea that Dr. Kudrat-e-Khuda's report is perfect. It is normal for the newly independent country to consider the government's restructuring of the libraries that are being supported by colonial thought and the next generation.

The Commission was responsible for the formulation of a policy of education as the Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman thought. This is reflected in the description of the following. The education policy of the newly independent country should be the same as that of anyone who accepts it. The discussions related to the library of the Commission of Dr. Kudrat-e-Khuda are briefly discussed.²⁴

1. Primary School Library

The responsibility of creating interest in books and raising the respect and the seeding to develop a habit to read books is to be given to the parents first, then to elementary school. But the responsibility is not being properly observed. So far, no development plan has been considered for the introduction of library in primary schools in this country. As a

result, the library can be set up in the sadar area and the delivery of books to primary schools can be arranged. One or more designated primary schools in each union must be used as a book camp. The government initiative will provide for the publication of beautiful books and magazines for children and distribution of them at a low cost.

2. Secondary School Library

The library is also much neglected in secondary schools. The lack of books, the lack of space, even the lack of librarians, the lack of inspiration for reading books among the students and teachers, above all, identifies the grim picture of secondary schools. The libraries of secondary schools have to be completely rebuilt. The country needs to focus on developing the lowest quality secondary schools in the country. The failure of the secondary school library to establish a library is a sure result of the failure of the attempt to establish the library at the college and university level.

3. College Library

The college libraries of the country are meserable basically like secondary schools. The state of the public colleges is a little better, but the plight of the libraries of private colleges is very much pronounced. Many colleges have recently been upgraded to degree level, in some college honors courses have been introduced, and some have been introduced to post-graduate classes. But there was no arrangement to expand the library of those colleges. The lowest standards of development of the size of the libraries are indicated by dividing colleges into three levels in the big, small and medium. The recommendations on the allocation and management of expenditure stake must be followed properly.

4. University Library

The library system at the university level is not satisfactory, according to the Commission. The university should take immediate action on the development of libraries. At this stage, need to be assessing the existing functionality and weakness of the libraries. The Commission should prepare a development projects based on assessment done and is needed to create library committee consistong of renowned librarians to coordinate and to provide necessary advice to universities. Meanwhile, the University Grants commission needs to be looked into.

The university will have to increase the allocation of books, develop the efficient reference services to strengthen research work and provide adequate foreign currency and government resources for foreign books, magazines, films, etc. for imports.

5. Public libraries

Public libraries in developed countries mean a law-based, tax-based cultural service institution, so that people have free access to resources of a collection, all-round public is a centre of life-long education. Students get a chance to access as when when the required. So students have a free access to use public libraries. Our national goal is to expand the public library across the country so that every citizen can get public library services within a mile of his or her residence. The Public Library Act will be therefore required to impose tax, setting up of trucks, build up of public library Directorate and setting up of public library advisory councils as Commission assumed.

The public library should be set up in Rajshahi immediately. The public library in Dhaka, Chittagong, and Khulna has to solve the problem of space and increase the book allocation by three times than earlier. Government assistance for private public libraries must be increased and necessary non-recurring approvals have to be provided. The Public Library of Bangladesh should be given copyright rights and the constitution of the Legislative Autonomous Institution and the Public Library Advisory Council should be established.

6. National Archives

To keep the rights of citizens and the state, collect and preserve the important records and original documents and primary archieves and to collect, preserve the basic documents of national history and research output establishing department of national archives and provide the national archives with the necessary facilities and appoint the National Archives Commission.

7. Library Training

The Education Commission's recommendation requires thousands of trained librarians and library staff to manage high quality libraries. The current training system is not enough to meet this requirement. The Department of Library Science at Rajshahi, Chittagong, and Jahangirnagar University is immense necessary to open and the Comission recommends that a single-pot library institute should be set up in Dhaka. The Commission also recommended that equally qualified librarians should be assigned to be equivalent to teachers as the rank and wage.

The recommendations were commissioned by the Commission but the Bangabandhu wanted a well-formed library system to help in the creation of a well-educated nation for generations to come. He also believed in the idea that if he could not build a nation of the most wanted, the most creative, the country would never be recognized as a better nation

on earth. So he signed the first constitution of Bangladesh on 14 December. He ordered for the creation of a short and long-term First-Year Plan for the development of the economic infrastructure. Reconstruction of administrative systems, rehabilitation of one crore people, development of broken communication systems, expand the education system, provide textbooks free to the students of primary and at a nominal cost to students of secondary level, establish Islamic foundation, establish madrasa education board, establish 11,000 new primary schools and 40,000 primary schools, women rehabilitation organisation for the poor women, set up a freedom fighter welfare trust for the freedom fighters, and more non-essential steps taken including exemption of levy for 25 bighas agricultural land. Through which he tried to build the socio-economic infrastructure and gradually turn the country into a prosperous country.

It is especially noteworthy that for a long time, from the pain and lack of various rock-colds in his prison life the Bangabandhu became a booklover. From 1948 onwards, except few days, until the return on 10 January 1972, in his lonely time the book was the only companion of the Bangabandhu. He did not find his family as he had survived with the book in his lonely life. He developed a deep sense of affection and intimate love for the books. He would have been more suffering than he was in prison. He would forget loneliness by looking at the book. Bangabandhu wrote: because there was no chance of talking to anyone in prison or being allowed to talk. So he used to spend time with the books. "I read books every day," he also wrote on Wednesday, 20 July 1966 in his diary: because I have no choice but to spend time. I'll talk to someone for a minute, and the government has stopped.²⁵ On Wednesday, 1 March 1967, the Bangabandhu re-wrote the same thing, "There is no choice but to read only the newspaper and book."²⁶ In fact he spent his lonely time reading newspapers and books in the jail. From loving books Bangabandhu affectionate for the library, it's very natural. He was happier to read books than to eat three meals. We can see the presence of loving books and affectionate to library in the Dr. Kudrat-e-Khuda's Report of the Education Commission. Earlier, in 1954, the reflection of loving books and libraries while he was laying Foundation of the Central Public Library building as a Minister of United Front Cabinet that was also an indication of revelation of love to library.

In this light, the National Archives and Library Department was established on 6 November 1972 on the orders of the Bangabandhu, first in a rented house in the Vooter Gally, Hatirpool, in order to preserve the valuable elements of the past history of the nation and literature and culture of the *Bengalis*. Under this Bangladesh National Archives was established. Later, the official notification was published in 1975. About twelve years later, the National Archives of Bangladesh was transferred to the National Library building in Agargaon, Sher-e-Banglanagar.

In a new initiative came into effect to pay honor the indomitable desire of the building Golden Bengal of the Bangabandhu, people were dedicated to the improve the socio-economic condition and to formation of a new nation, and the preparation started to rebuild the break down, burnt or destroyed and looted libraries of schools, colleges of villages. The government of Bangabandhu formed a committee in 1973 to improve the public library. The appropriate steps were taken at the appropriate time to develop the library on the sole instructions of the Bangabandhu administration. A plan was adopted with an allocation of Tk. 2,40,63,000.00.²⁷

The government of Bangabandhu is also focused on taking special libraries to the standard level, including the development of public libraries. He felt priority for the up grading and development of education systems and research for the development of the socio-economic conditions of the newly independent damaged country in a manner of fastest time. The libraries associated with various governments, private and autonomous institutions, organizations, industries, museum etc. are emphasized to build up and take to a standard level was also immensely felt. Many of these special libraries have become more efficient and superior to public libraries and educational institutions. These are the main things to address that the country and the nation believed in.

In 1974, in his address as a Chief Guest at the International Conference of the Bangla Academy, Banga Bandhu ordered to establish a public library at the each *Thana* (police station), he referred to Dr. Kudrat-e-Khuda Education Commission. The conference was chaired by Professor Dr. Mazharul Islam. It is noted that the country felt the inadequacy of the library movement from the hunger for reading books, and focused on the establishment of new libraries, including the reconstruction of public libraries, including schools, colleges and university libraries, in the newly independent country.

But we are unfortunate professionals and nation as well. The great man who gave us a red-green emblemed flag to stand up on the earth, such a great man ever born who left his bedroom to establish the library, who dreamed to build up Golden Bangla by reading books, thought of building a sovereign Bangladesh that would be decorated like lines of a book— what would have been said if not a great man with a heart like a great ocean—"I am alone, books and newspapers are my friends." I drown myself in this" (cited from 'কারাগারের রোজনামা'). Such unique man of unique mind, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, was killed by some aberrated and errant assassins who broke their undead bullets the Great Man of the World. The greatest man of the thousand years of the Bengalis killed along with his favorite books and family. And we lost our real book and library lover on the dark night of 15 August 1975. That's an end of glorious era of the century.

4. From the late '75 to the present

After the 1313 day rule of the Bangabandhu era and the establishment of the country as an independent state, the arrangements were made to establish the country's libraries. It is obvious that even though the country's public libraries have not seen much progress during the period of independence, special libraries have improved significantly.²⁸

It is mentioned here that the government public library was established at three divisional headquarters in the country during the pre-independence period but the Rajshahi Divisional Public Library was established in 1983 after independence.²⁹

This is how it lasts for a long time. The library development is fully stagnant for while. Bangabandhu's Bangladesh has only shaped a cocoon to be unveiled as a butterfly he dreamt to making the Golden Bangla as a colorful butterfly. He wanted to see the colorful butterfly flies opening its wings in front him. He will enjoy the beauty of flying butterfly. It Needs sometime to be matured. The silkworm which he rescued from the garbage (debris) required a proper environment to be grown up. He thought how to achieve the ultimate goal. But the last one didn't. The cluster is full of butterfly-colored wings and cannot fly no more. The golden Bangla of the dream of the king of the Bangladesh was again transformed into a *sunshan* burning ground by the murderer.

After 15 August 1975, all the previous activities were invalid or abandoned. Like many, the plan for the development of the library was not taken up in the post independent of Bangladesh.³⁰ The development and education activities were stalled by the military rule. "After almost a decade of independence, in 1981, in collaboration with the Ministry of Sports and Culture and the British Council, British citizen J. S. Parker conducted a survey on the Public Library of Bangladesh. In February 1982, a national seminar titled 'Library Development' was held in a joint initiative of the British Council and the Ministry of Sports and Culture. At the seminar, the survey report compiled by J. S. Parker was discussed.³¹ An editorial by the writer of this essay was published in the '*Banglar Bani*', discussing on the output of the seminar immediately after the seminar was concluded.

It is especially noteworthy that the central public library in Dhaka and three other divisional public libraries were functioning at the government level in the country until the establishment of the current Library Department in 1984. Later, under the project 'Development of Central Public Library' in Bangladesh, adopted in 1980-81³², the Central Public Library was centralized and the structure of a public library was approved in the country. Meanwhile, in 1982 the then 'Bangladesh Council' was declared as a "dissolution" by the government and the Military Law Committee (ANM Committee) on administrative restructuring recommended the formation of a 'Department of Public Library' in the country with the government public libraries and the various levels of information centres/libraries of the disbanded Bangladesh Council. Under the Department, library services are currently being provided to the general public through 71 public libraries. According to the Library Director- 2014 published by the National Book Centre, "the number of non-government public libraries is 1065; of these, 112 libraries are over 50 years old. . . . The total of Tk. 23 million allocated in the financial year 2016-2017 for the development of non-government public libraries.³⁵

Besides, the move to speed up the library movement was not taken very well. In 1972 and 1976, two seminars were held in Dhaka by the Bangladesh Library Association. After all, the development of the library is very slow. No new library is known to have been created at this time.

Library Science Education System

It has been mentioned earlier that the first library science education was taken up under the supervision of W. C. Borden of Boroda in 1911. Then in 1915 and 1929, the education system was started in Punjab and Madras respectively and training was started in Lahore under the supervision of American Librarian Asa Don Dickenson. From there, Khan Bahadur Asadullah Khan, the founder of the Kolkata Imperial Library, famous for his work as the founder of the Indian Library Movement, received library trainings along with many other famous professionals from Bangladesh.

Long after that, the first three-month certificate course was introduced in 1952 with the initiative and effort of the then Librarian Late Fazle Elahi at Dhaka University Library under the Faculty of Arts.³⁶ Later, in the 1955-56 academic year, Miss Millared L Methvan taught the certificate course in the Fulbright Scholarship Programme. In 1958, the full curriculum was started with the introduction of the Department of Library Science at Dhaka University.³⁷ It was a six-month certificate course. In total, four courses are run in a series. Later, in the academic year 1959-1960 and 1962-1963, Postgraduate Diploma and Master's Degree courses in library science were started respectively under Dhaka University.³⁸ After the closure of Fulbright Scholarships, the six-month certificate course was launched in 1958 by the then East Pakistan Library Association. At the same time, following curriculum taught at the University of London, introduced a one year duration Postgraduate Diploma courses in the 1959-1960 academic year at Dhaka University. A one year Master's of Arts course was introduced for the students those who were already passed the Postgraduate Diploma Course at Dhaka University in 1962. The Masters of Arts course started very successfully from the academic year 1962-1963. The academic year 1964-1965 of Library science education was opened the horizon as a model of development in Bangladesh. From this academic year, the library science course was recognized and organized as a full fledged 'Department of Library Science' under the Faculty of Arts.³⁹

In 1974-75, the two-year duration 'Masters of Philosophy' (MPhil) program was approved by the Dhaka University Syndicate⁴⁰ and the course was started from the academic year 1975-1976.⁴¹ At the end of the academic year, another

two-year course titled 'Masters of Arts' was approved; the first year of which will be the Preliminary and the second year will be treated as the 'Masters of Arts' Final.⁴² The postgraduate diploma course also continued in parallel at the same time. The 'Doctor of Philosophy' (PhD) program in library science was also approved by Dhaka University Syndicate from the academic year 1978-79⁴³ and the program started from year. As a result, the scope of the department's work is greatly enhanced as a whole.

During this time, the Bangladesh Association of Librarians, Information Scientists and Documentalists (BALID) has been making long-term requests and petitions with the authorities for renaming the Department and introducing honors courses. Dhaka University authorities has taken the proposal into consideration and later decided to introduce the Honors course. From academic year 1987-1988, three year duration Bachelor of Arts (BA Honors) course in library and information science has approved.⁴⁴ At the same time, the Department was renamed as the "Department of Library and Information Science" after keeping it in harmony with the era of information technology. With the introduction of the Honors Course, the Postgraduate Diploma Course was abolished and the Bangladesh Library Association was forced to take over the course.⁴⁵ The course was started in 1989 but for unknown reasons the Association failed to conduct the course. Which is later run by a self-interested group through setting up an institute under the National University, although the Bangladesh Library Association is the only one who is the founder of the institute?

From 1991-92, the ongoing degree (pass) and graduate (honors) level were introduced library and information science as subsidiary subjects in colleges under Dhaka University.⁴⁶ From 1994-95, Dhaka University started a two-year Postgraduate (MA) course.⁴⁷ Also in the academic year 1997-98, Dhaka University Authorities introduced four year graduate (honors) program to cope with the Western systems instead of three-year undergraduate program in the field of information science and library management. The four year graduate (honors) program was declared as a professional degree instead of a three-year graduate course from the academic year 1999-2000.⁴⁸ The decision of the authority came into effective from the academic year 1997-98.⁴⁹

Dhaka University Authorities approved to change the name of the Department of Library and Information Science as Department of Information Science and Library Management in the academic year 2001-2002 and took a commendable step of internationalization by renaming the Department.⁵⁰

Apart from Dhaka University, Rajshahi University started a one year postgraduate diploma course from session 1991-1992.⁵¹ Department of Library and Information Science announced that the three-year Library and Information Science (Honors) program in Social Science and launched from the academic year 1992-1993.⁵² The one-year postgraduate degree course in Social Science (MSS)⁵³ and a 4 year duration honors program was introduced instead of the three-year duration program from the academic session 1997-1998.

In 1992, the National University launched its educational programme. On the demand of the Bangladesh Association of Librarians, Information Scientists and Documentalists (BALID), National University opened the windows of opportunity to take 400 number of optional subjects in the library and information science in the graduate (pass) courses was introduced in the academic year 1998-1999. Besides, there are also opportunities to study libraries and information science in three colleges under the National University, meanwhile, the number college may be increased.

Library Associations

Though the necessary steps to speed up the library movement in the present situation are not taken very well, some organizations are playing a vital role in meeting and developing the demands of the library professionals and professionals in the country. Among them, the name of the Bangladesh Library Association (LAB) is mentioned. The Bangladesh Library Association was established in 1956 by some of the best personalities to serve as a bargaining platform for the development of the country's library professions and professionals. A total of 13 members were responsible for the functioning of the Executive Council. The President, Secretary and Treasury were the Late Muhammad Siddique Khan, Raqib Hasan and Abdur Rahman Mrida respectively hold chair. Besides, 10 more were in charge of the Functional Council. Later, many other Executive Councils were formed and he took up professional duties. But there was no development activity. There was a complete void in the professional field for a long time.

The effort to exercise direct voting rights with the help of Dr. Muhammad Abdussattar, and Mr. Abdul Mannan, the librarian of the Nutrition and Food Institute, Dhaka University, succeeded. As a result, the first Executive Council of the Bangladesh Library Association was elected in 2004 by applying direct voting rights. In this election, Professor Dr. Muhammad Abdussattar and Syed Ali Akbar were elected as president and general secretary respectively. The Council has been successful in its work till 2008 and has made unprecedented progress in the field of professionalism. The Association has been publishing a newsletter titled 'Upatta' and a journal titled 'Eastern Librarian'. The first issue Upatta brought out in light by Dr. Md. Adussattar in 1990 during the Executive Council headed by Late Abdun Nur and M.Shamsul Islam Khan respectively. Also, LAB is conducting a six month certificate course. During the time of the Executive Council elected in 1998-2000, a directory of LAB members was published under the supervision and editing of Professor Dr. Muhammad Abdussattar.⁵³

Traveling a Long Road to professional development Bangladesh Library Association has created a state of stagnation when there is no provision for the promotion of professionals and professionalism. There was a great frustration among

the professionals, then a group of young generation and comparatively young professionals were spontaneously organized. On a fine day of dawn, absolutely a professional organization was established in the open green courtyard of the Dhaka University Language Institute under the title 'Bangladesh Association of Young Librarians Information Scientists and Documentalists' (BAYLID). An 11 members committee was formed.⁵⁴ Shafiq Mahmood Mannan was appointed as the Chairman of the Ad-hoc Committee (23.01.1986-25.4.1986). Three months later, the first effective council with 18 members was formed in 26.04.1986; the first Chairperson and Secretary General of the Council was the then-Mohammed Abdussattar and Md. Haroon-ur-Rashid. The first created title was partially changed discarding the word 'young' and the registration of the Social Welfare Department was obtained by determining the current title of the BALID. Currently its Bengali title is 'Bangladesh Granthagarik O Tattyanbid Samiti' and English title is 'Bangladesh Association of Librarians Information Scientists and Documentationists' (BALID). So far, the library has been performing a variety of developmental activities with great dedication and confidence. BALID published a magazine titled 'Informatics'. It has an institute; Mr. Shamsuddin Ahmed was the first Director of the institute. In addition, some specialized professional organizations are also conducting career development activities from their own positions.

Preparedness to compete on the highway of information technology

In the current world, information is considered to be an indispensable resource. We are also living in the information. Now, information based nation is recognized as wealthy nation than a financially wealthy one. That who has more information, the nation wealthier is. Information plays a helpful role in national development and economic development. Only three decades ago, the situation was different. The nature of the information explosion and the variety of information were the cause of the problem for the users. But that anxiety is no longer there. The use of new information technology in the field of information collection, processing, preservation, retrieving and distribution has been transformed into a 'information revolution'. In fact, the world that is separated by the information revolution has now become a fragmented world. The world is now recognized as a continuous information village in the process of information flow. The technical knowledge and techniques used in the information service are now identified as 'information and communication technology' in the new phase.⁵⁵

"The universal feeling of solidarity among people has been expanded and awakened to increase the use of information and communication technology. Everything seems to be very closer. Quality changes have also been made in everyday life, education, literature and communication. Inspired by this understanding in the mid-nineties, the then Vice President Mr. Elgore was instrumental in making the children of the United States a 'global citizen'.⁵⁶ This realization is a little late but it has awakened us. It is not right to delay the creation of a national development system and the continuous free flow of information, only from the base ground to the creation of efficient human resources. During the 1313 days of rule, the father of the nation, The Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, also dreamed of creating Golden Bangla by creating efficient human resources. His only successful successor is today's Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina is trying to implement the dream of Bangabandhu.

"With the development and support of information technology, Bangladesh is already pursuing the goal of creating digital Bangladesh. In conjunction with the world trends, the office-courts have ensured that information is available and quickly accessible, especially in libraries and information centers using 'information and communication technology'. The new horizons have been opened in the modern information infrastructure through the launch of the Bangla satellite. Online networking systems have brought about a change in information management, including computer-based online and offline technologies. In information management the offline and online networking systems have reduced the wide range of data explosions. Access to international online databases has created opportunities to travel on information highways. It is worth mentioning that in the mid-nineties, during the rule of Awami League Government, Bangladesh was connected to Internet in the information highway. Since then, the door to access to digital full text from digital reference has been opened. Some private universities and international institutions have taken the initiative to quickly take this opportunity and a small number of university libraries have taken the initiative to subscribe the concerned organizations for access to digital full text. Earlier in the 80s, "Documentation: a new concept" (in Bengali তথ্যায়ন: একটি নতুন ধারণা) was added a new dimension to the library and information service of Bangladesh.⁵⁷ In particular, international organizations and domestic special organizations were able to attract the attention of the concerned service customers through 'documentation' services in the field of information management. The organizations are innovative in providing documentation services like as the bibliographic services such as current awareness, content analysis, SDI, document review, document reproduction and other informational services.

The main goal of development is to make it so easier to solve everyday problems in human life and to improve physical and mental health. Without the real development of the nature of the mass people, the results of the state development are not expected.⁵⁸ . . . The need for understanding the emotions and moods, the expectations and the needs, and the completeness of national socio-economic life requires the development of the masses. Mass people are those who live in the rural areas. They need to convey information to them in order to understand their senses or their own entity.

The Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib wanted to set up a library in the village to make the 'Golden Bangla' (সোনার বাংলা) with the enriched people. The 'information for development' has taken a significant place in modern development arena. Development and information complement one another. The rural information system was generated from this concept, was established in 2010. During the second time, the Awami League government established by union information and services centres across the country and introduced a period of change in information management. The union information and services centre (UISC) was set up across the country on 11 November 2010 as part of the establishment of 'Digital Bangladesh' to convey the benefits of information to the public at grassroots level. A total of 4547 UISCs have been established across the country so far.⁵⁹ The UISC newsletter published by Access to Information Programs shows that around 32 million people take the UISC service every month. Of these, 78,000 are women (70% of whom are women). From UISC, mobile banking services, 30,200 people life insurance services, 35,000 people (70% of whom are women) telemedicine services and 45,000 people receive computer training services.⁶⁰

If the service system continues, the nationality, unity and tradition will be expanded in the efforts to improve the mass people. Similarly, the socio-economic conditions, education, life and livelihood cultural results will be made public. In this context, it should be noted that a network of public library services should be created in each union to develop the common education and education of the people of this country to fulfill the dreams of the people of the country. It will make it easier to provide life and livelihood information. ``Because the main condition of development is mass education. Library is one of the main means of mass education. Therefore, it is essential to establish a public library that is expanded and integrated in the country.''⁶¹ Then the mass education will be expanded. This requires the creation of national library and information policy. The policy followed to increase wealth in the rich and prosperous countries of the world is a policy of cooperation. What is needed for a prosperous country is essential for a poor country. The "Fermiton Plan" is well-known in the library world in the United States for following the policy of collaborative collection in every possible field, especially in the development of library collection and use. . . . Implementing the plan according to that proposal is essential in today's socio-economic context.⁶²

In the 1990s, two researchers from the Department of Information Science and Library Management, Dhaka University⁶³ sought to consider the recommendations of the opportunity to take steps to meet the needs of the country's population by establishing a 'Central database' and sharing information on the development of integrated libraries and information systems in a higher study. On the other hand, the networking provides a free flow of information and guides each other to build information resources through sharing.

But the fact that the national information management and resource sharing is not taken seriously at the right time has not made it possible to build a "central database". The most important aspect of the creation of 'Digital Bangladesh' is a well-organized central database and information system. Under which all the relevant documents and documents of all professions of the country including the information generated by the government will be preserved. As part of the new technology, it may be timely to make the right information available at the right time as per the needs of the right people through digital information processing, subject-based classification, and the right to save the information. Only if this decision is implemented will the dream of developing the 'Digital Bangladesh' shall be fulfilled.

Recommendations

1. In order to consolidate the country's library and information system, it is essential to formulate a plan similar to Farmington Plan in the United States.
2. To make library and information services accessible at all levels in line with the recommendations of Dr. Kudrat-e-Khuda Education Commission directed by Bangabandhu for implantation of UNESCO SDG-2030, especially Education Agenda -4.
3. Establish a library in each police station, which Bangabandhu used to desire.
4. The formulation and implementation of Library and Information Policy is now the demand of the age.
5. To change the concept of library and information services and to take integrated planning and administrative steps to ensure better services.
6. To create adequate funding opportunities so that information services are disrupted.
7. To create opportunities for professionals to receive technical training for timeliness and skill enhancement.
8. Emphise on practical education related to information technology in library and information science education curriculum.
9. To increase the technical facilities in the library and information system including construction of physical infrastructure.
10. Creating opportunities for free and uninterrupted online information through satellite integration in libraries and information systems.
11. It is time to build a central information hub to deliver timely information services at the grassroots level. To adopt national policy and action plan with the help of experienced and skilled professionals in this regard.

12. It is important to introduce the Public Library Act to make the service activities of the public libraries for the public.
13. Existing public libraries need to be developed soon as a school of thought based, intellectual development technology-based knowledge for children.
14. The time has come to introduce digital library and information services using the latest experience by ensuring uninterrupted power-flow.
15. The goal of building a Digital Bangladesh can be achieved by implanting administrative activities with the help of experienced and skilled professionals in the existing libraries and information service organizations.

Conclusion

The history of library organizations in Bangladesh is not insignificant. But Bangladesh has a much more heritage than many developed countries in the world. But at different times, even the exploiters of the colonial rulers have repeatedly stumbled upon Bangabandhu's golden Bangla in the threshing floor of racial discrimination. Bangla has been scarred by the fierce nails claws for thousands of years. Bangabandhu's Sonar Bangla tasted liberation from the oppression and exploitation of the Pals, Mughals, Portuguese, French, English, and most recently Pakistanis. The time that Bangabandhu used to stay awake in the available time of his life was all about Bangla, Bengali and the books, books, books and for the thought of library. When he found time after 100 years of the time of the period, he founded the foundation stone of the Public Library in 1958; He made a glorious history.

One hundred years after the subjugation, when the time came, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman laid foundation stone of the public library in 1954; and he made a glorious history. There is no precedent for any Bengali to inaugurate a library before in this country. Hundreds of years after that undisputed leader of Bengal planted a sapling under a slender tree in the yearning of an unsatisfied soul which is swinging in our hearts as a mahiruh. Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, he was a book, only a book and library lover. He has read books for so long in his life that he couldn't give so much time to his family.

His ultimate goal was to build a golden Bangla. Bangabandhu was convinced to give the gift of an educated, intelligent, talented, creative, thoughtful, knowledgeable and enlightened nation. It was here that we were blessed as a Bengali Nation. We are a nation of misfortune! For twenty years of accursed time, the fate of the nation was smitten by the darkness of evil rule.

In a film titled "Unknown Wind" of Taliganj, Mejo Kakamani replied in a response to a question from his niece 'Deepa', "The trees don't talk, they just heap up." What exactly do the trees speak about? Only to heap up for a generation. There are many more creations in the world that can bring together and preserved about civilization, history, culture, words, knowledge to enlighten the generations. Whatever the trees preserve, to match the answer to the curiosity of the future generations. Beside the trees and stones, etc., human being are the best creation of the Creator; A library under a tree is created by human beings to find a way to reach the next generation of immortal creations of knowledge emanating from human thought-consciousness, thinking practice and intellect. "The words of all the people of the past are all preserved near the tree"; the girl hears and says then "I will listen too."

Have we been able to plant that tree? Sitting on that ground we will listen to the people who of the past. Create a library as bearer of immortality of civilization is one of the main elements of all the excellence of creation. If not, now is the time to encourage people who are interested in planting trees to cultivate the mindset to develop the spirit of library creation.

The Bangabandhu planted the seeds of that mind and mentality in 1954, in 1971, in 1972, in 1974, in the end, in terms of torn of life with bullets in his own home; As if a cocoon takes the form of a planted plant, so the great man of the Bengalis of a thousand years wanted see it in the form of butterfly.

Its need some time to get perfection. Let's cherish and nurture the seed of the cocoon picked from the rubble. Why don't we create a beautiful environment and make the cocoon a colorful butterfly? If we can take care of it a little, then the whole nation will enjoy the beauty of the colorful butterfly. We will be blessed again as Bangabandhu wanted to make people happy. Let's get free from filth of the curse. So, only then will Bangabandhus's dream of Sonar Bangla become a true like that colorful butterfly.

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